

The return of the Cabinets of Wonder. The Library 2040 – a Utopia

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Abstract: The impact of the digital transformation on scholarly communication is still underestimated, and with it the transformation of the library. The increasing dissolution of familiar media forms and the progressing cross-linking of digital resources will turn the library of 2040 into a new form of cabinet of wonders that will arrange knowledge differently but will continue to exhibit past forms in the range of their curiosities.

Keywords: Library, Utopia, Cabinet of Wonders

The digital transformation is changing society in a similarly fundamental way as the introduction of writing transformed oral society. Digitization is therefore not just one tool among others, where we are free to choose without changing anything else - instead of a screwdriver, I reach for a cordless screwdriver, and otherwise a screw remains a screw. Instead, writing gave society a different understanding of space-time and made different economies, settlements, and forms of government possible - in other words, it changed almost everything. We see something very similar in the digital transformation, and this also affects libraries.

Original digital media are a case of »re-mediation«: they do not completely reinvent themselves, but revive from earlier media forms what is relevant to them¹ - for example, from medieval manuscripts, which for Seb Falk are by no means static objects: „Later users could add color or commentary in the margins, amend mistakes, fill in diagrams where they were lacking, give the work a new title or add the (supposed) author's name or simply sketch in a doodle.“² A remediation of the epoch of manuscripts (and partly of the oral society) is laid out very early in the

¹ Cf. Bolter and Grusin (1998).

² Falk (2021) 125. Krommer (2021) draws the link to digital media: <https://twitter.com/mediendidaktik/status/1445490522198396933>

digital transformation of scholarship, if one compares the cited practice of the Middle Ages with the Budapest Declaration on Open Access of 2003:

„By »open access« to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself.“³

This makes it even more obvious how untenable the current state of affairs is, where the frozen, static knowledge representations of the print age are digitally recreated as club goods in order to exclude either readers or authors from the discourse. This is not science - nor is it a library. But what could steps towards a library of the digital look like?

Central for this development of a new library is the expansion and redefinition of their curating activities. Libraries have always been selecting and making references, for instance, through display and presentation. For some time now, this has been expanding to include the library as a venue, its spaces, services, and participatory outreach to target groups.⁴ Of course, there is also the opposite movement, which assigns rarity value to industrial products and seeks happiness in redundancy.⁵ But the fundamental mission of libraries remains, as it has for centuries, to be the essential institution where knowledge lives - as in the case histories of Citizen Science and Open GLAM strategies presented by Werner. There is therefore no objective reason why digitization should change this central role, unless libraries themselves were to abandon it.

By 2040, data curation will be an everyday part of library curation. Scientists have been generating and sharing source code since the 1950s. Since the 1980s, researchers have been filling databases with research data from large-scale projects. Since the 1990s, digital research data has increasingly become the norm in individual laboratories as well. Whereas before it was primarily findings distilled from data and calculations that entered the collections of libraries, developments over the past 70 years fundamentally changed our attitude toward these sources of knowledge. Historically, museums and collections, not libraries, used to be responsible for research materials, equipment and technology. Today, digitization is blurring the lines between source and insight: more intellectual energy is often put

³ Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002).

⁴ Cf. Werner (2021).

⁵ Cf. Brintzinger (2020).

into collecting data or creating source code than into summarizing the results. Sometimes the insight itself is much easier to describe than the path to it: „I think we have it“ was the summary sentence at the press conference on the discovery of the Higgs boson.⁶

Modern research therefore requires an infrastructure that takes this transformed way of working into account. Whereas in the early 20th century electricity, water and gas in the laboratories, as well as full bookshelves and good catalogues in the libraries were usually sufficient, now infrastructure components are required that support the creation, processing, evaluation and making accessible of research data and source code in a manner as invisible as a light switch, a socket or a faucet - and are therefore just as indispensable. Of course, one could create a dedicated infrastructure unit specifically for this purpose, but due to its historical expertise and tasks, it is already there with the library: metadata competence, automated workflows, institutional stability that has not only collected media in many forms for centuries, but also produced them itself - all of this will be needed more than ever in 2040, and even more the mentality of librarians who desire nothing more than good service and solutions for those who turn to them.

From the researcher perspective, automated source code and data capture during the research phase allows efficient work and focus on the essentials. Competent on-site support is crucial here. Even after all data has been collected and all errors have been removed from the source code and the transition to the publication phase is imminent, competent support is essential to process data, code and text(s) in such a way that the intended audience can understand and continue the research process and the insights gained from it. Finally, it must be decided in which form which of these projects should be archived for the long term or deleted after appropriate deadlines. Research, communication, selective archiving: each of these steps requires expertise that has always been located in libraries.

Research. Even 30 years after digitization has entered most laboratories, institutional support for documenting research processes, collecting research data, and creating source code is the exception, not the rule. Electronic lab notebooks have been used by researchers for decades, but rarely are they provided by their institution. For more than 40 years, various research fields have operated databases for research data - but almost all of them are financed by more or less precarious project funds, so that every year a large part of them faces extinction. The first cases of documented code sharing date back to punched tape codes of the 1950s.

⁶ Cf. <https://home.cern/news/series/lhc-physics-ten/higgs-boson-what-makes-it-special>

Today, commercial platforms such as Sourceforge, Bitbucket, but especially GitHub are used. None of these solutions enjoys institutional support; instead, GitHub, where presumably by far the largest portion of scientific source code currently resides, was purchased by Microsoft, a corporation with a reputation for simply shutting down anything that does not generate sufficient profit and in some cases destroying the digital objects stored there, such as MS Books or MS Academic.⁷

Research today means that researchers must place themselves at the mercy of precarious infrastructures that have all too often discovered the exploitation of user data as a business model.⁸ This is just as unacceptable for the (in some countries constitutionally) protected area of academic freedom as it is for the interests of research funders. The Library 2040 will trigger enormous improvements here. Analogous to an email address, all researchers will receive addresses for research data and source code from the institution, so that they can concentrate on research and do not have to waste time or effort finding the right tools in terms of content and funding, where there is also a constant fear that the valuable digital objects will not be given the required lifespan. Accessibility, reliability, competence, and efficiency will enter research with Library 2040, where inefficiency and tinkering are mostly commonplace today.

Communication. The consequences of the lack of institutional support continue in the communication phase. It starts with the creation of publications, where today collaborative authoring systems are commonly offered by the data cartels (instead of scholarly institutions) with the risks mentioned above. But what is probably even more pernicious is that science is currently being digitized in a typically academic way: Instead of actual remediation, allowing data, software, and text to flow into one another other as in 'literate programming' and thus becoming transparently explicable, we have created separate and barely interoperable silos, making science even harder to understand and verify than it already is. Such digitally transformed scholarship will be even more exclusionary than the current one, where an illusion of accessibility is maintained via digitally imitated print media: 'here it is'. In this illusion, each reader experiences their non-understanding as an

⁷ See for example <https://www.windowcentral.com/microsoft-closing-its-digital-book-store-windows-10> and <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2021/05/27/goodbye-microsoft-academic-hello-open-research-infrastructure/>

⁸ Cf. DFG (2021) and Sarah Lamdan: Data Cartels. The Companies That Control and Monopolize Our Information. Stanford 2023.

individual failure. A Jupyterhub or a GitHub repository alone, not as part of a networked knowledge representation, is now even less comprehensible, the distance of the experts to everyone else grows and the legitimacy of science dwindles.

Again, a Library 2040 seems like the most sensible solution: institutionalized authoring systems that allow authorized users to write collaboratively, without the fear of someone reading along who has not been explicitly added. Seamless integration of research data and source code to make findings reproducible and understandable. Competent on-site support broadens the target audience of the final product or its derivatives. With the involvement of interested target groups, e.g., digital civil society. The Library 2040 would thus not only be the central core facility for digitized research on each campus, but also a living inclusion and central place for exchange, mediation and further learning. Involved in the Third Mission in this way, the Library 2040 will become one of the main pillars of the knowledge society. Accessing the world's knowledge will become multidimensional: collections, texts, data and software will be linked digitally and will also have their meaning in this linkage. Semantic Web technologies will become central to the way we work in the Library 2040.

Archiving. It is already common experience for many libraries that publication services maximize their proximity to researchers. Resuming the old tradition that a library not only stores media but is also a place where they are produced, mitigates and potentially reverses a development that would otherwise result in all their researchers' texts being archived off-site - at least in those fields of study that publish in journals. This would marginalize libraries to the printed works of a shrinking range of disciplines. The Library 2040, however, has turned its publication servers into a central mission: to select the work of its institution's researchers and preserve it in a way that stores contributions to knowledge and makes them understandable. Curators work in Library 2040 to weave science across time in multimedia, allowing research to continue seamlessly.

If we want to sum up our utopia in one buzzword, Library 2040 will be a new form of a Cabinet of Wonders. Historically, Cabinets of Wonders predated the split between the modern museum on the one hand and the scholarly utility library on the other. They collected across everything with quite different intentions: to reflect a cosmological order, to affirm the ruler's power of definition over the world or as a teaching collection, as in the well-documented example of the Francke Foundations.⁹ Such cabinets were often intertwined with science, and some were

⁹ See Müller-Bahlke (2012).

of astonishing scope: the 1587 inventory of the Saxon Art Chamber of Elector August lists more than 7,000 tools and devices, as well as more than 400 scientific instruments and clocks.¹⁰ The example of the Francke Foundations, on the other hand, is also particularly valuable historically, because both the teaching collection and the historical library¹¹ have been preserved, and thus the fork in the road to specialized knowledge institutions is still visible. This splitting and specialization is now reversed: the digital linking of many knowledge resources takes our thinking and knowledge organization out of the linear character of a Western-influenced print age again - just as it has always remained a foreign body for many cultures.¹² Science and research will thus become more networked and think differently than they are accustomed to today, but this networking will in many cases also correspond to on-site linking: the library of 2040 will not be a purely digital library, but will demonstrate and explain knowledge formations that are no longer commonplace. It will be the place where the Third Mission is concentrated, where lifelong learning takes place, where science also translates into a wider public. And developed in that way, the library will also continue to be both a familiar and a trustworthy place - which is essential for science: free thinking and reflection need the *ou tópos*, the other place, where also the extraction logic of data cartels stops.

¹⁰ Cf. *Dresdener Kunstblätter* 1 (2016) 7.

¹¹ Klosterberg und Götze (2007).

¹² Cf. Weinberg (2015).

References:

- Bolter, Jay David; Grusin, Richard (1998): Remediation. Understanding New Media. Cambridge, Ma.: MIT Press.
- Brintzinger, Klaus-Rainer (2020): Warum Giraffen manchmal sterben müssen. Oder: Warum wir die Erwartungen an den Umgang mit den Büchern nicht erfüllen können. In: Köstner-Pemsel, Christina; Stadler, Elisabeth; Stumpf, Markus (Hrsg.) (2020): Künstliche Intelligenz in Bibliotheken: 34. Österreichischer Bibliothekartag Graz 2019 / *Schriften der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare (VÖB)*, Bd. 15, 219-233; DOI: [10.25364/guv.2020.voeb15](https://doi.org/10.25364/guv.2020.voeb15)
- Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002): Read the Declaration, <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>
- DFG (2021): Datentracking in der Wissenschaft: Aggregation und Verwendung bzw. Verkauf von Nutzungsdaten durch Wissenschaftsverlage. Bonn. https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/programme/lis/datentracking_papier_de.pdf
- Falk, Seb (2021): The Light Ages. A Mediaval Journal of Discovery. London: Penguin.
- Klosterberg, Britta; Götz Klaus E. (2007): Die Bibliothek der Franckeschen Stiftungen. Halle: Verlag der Franckeschen Stiftungen.
- Lamdan, Sarah (2023): Data Cartels. The Companies that Control and Monopolize Our Information. Stanford.
- Müller-Bahlke, Thomas (2012): Die Wunderkammer der Franckeschen Stiftungen. Halle: Verlag der Franckeschen Stiftungen.
- Weinberg, Ulrich (2015): Network Thinking. Was kommt nach dem Brockhaus-Denkmal? Hamburg: Murmann.
- Weltsicht und Wissen. Dresdener Kunstblätter 1/2016.